
INDISTILL: INFORMATION FLOW-PRESERVING KNOWLEDGE DISTILLATION FOR MODEL COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we introduce InDistill, a model compression approach that combines knowledge distillation and channel pruning in a unified framework for the transfer of the critical information flow paths from a heavyweight teacher to a lightweight student. Such information is typically collapsed in previous methods due to an encoding stage prior to distillation. By contrast, InDistill leverages a pruning operation applied to the teacher’s intermediate layers reducing their width to the corresponding student layers’ width. In that way, we force architectural alignment enabling the intermediate layers to be directly distilled without the need of an encoding stage. Additionally, a curriculum learning-based training scheme is adopted considering the distillation difficulty of each layer and the critical learning periods in which the information flow paths are created. The proposed method surpasses state-of-the-art performance on three standard benchmarks, i.e. CIFAR-10, CUB-200, and FashionMNIST by 3.08%, 14.27%, and 1% mAP, respectively, as well as on more challenging evaluation settings, i.e. ImageNet and CIFAR-100 by 1.97% and 5.65% mAP, respectively. The code is available at <https://github.com/gsarridis/InDistill.git>.

1 Introduction

The constant effort to increase the performance of Deep Neural Networks (DNN) has resulted in much deeper architectures that require massive compute power and memory to train and deploy. Also, several application settings have created the need to deploy DNNs at hardware with limited resources, which has given rise to the domain of model compression. During the past years, model compression has attracted a lot of research interest and many pertinent approaches have been proposed such as parameter pruning, quantization, low-rank factorization and knowledge distillation [1, 2].

The objective of Knowledge Distillation (KD), which constitutes one of the most effective ways for model compression [2, 3], is to transfer knowledge from a powerful teacher network to a smaller and faster one, in order to extend its performance capabilities. Early KD approaches aim at transferring the teacher’s last layer [4]. This enables smaller models to understand how the bigger models perceive the training data, but the lack of intermediate layer supervision impedes the learning of how the information flows through the teacher’s layers reducing the student’s generalization

Figure 1: Illustration of InDistill. Channel pruning is applied on the teacher’s intermediate layers, so that teacher and student models’ widths coincide for $l \in (1, L_g - 1)$. Then, the curriculum learning scheme suggests transferring each layer separately, as it is depicted on the right side, where \mathcal{S}_i denotes the layer’s i set of epochs. Learning the penultimate layer (i.e., L_g) can be achieved leveraging any knowledge distillation approach.

potential [5]. To remedy, recent KD methods [6, 7] have focused on transferring intermediate layers as well. However, the typically existing width discrepancy between teacher and student imposes an encoding stage that impairs information flow preservation, which is of utmost importance for imitating the teacher’s workings.

Pruning approaches are applied to reduce the storage requirements or the inference time of a DNN [1, 8, 9]. Unstructured pruning methods remove unimportant weights reducing the model’s storage size, while structured pruning methods [10, 11, 12, 13, 14] remove the less important CNN filters reducing both the model’s storage size and processing time. Furthermore, there have been efforts to combine KD and pruning for model compression, specifically [15] proposes applying KD after pruning only to the untouched layers during the pruning phase, and [16] introduces an approach that utilizes KD for fine-tuning a pruned model. However, pruning a teacher model in order to achieve architectural alignment with the student and directly distill intermediate layers has not yet been considered.

Furthermore, it is well known that during the training process a neural network undergoes several phases [17]. More precisely, the first training epochs are considered responsible for the creation of the model’s information flow paths. This fact has been taken into consideration by [5] in order to effectively distill intermediate layers, by adopting a suitable learning scheme based on that idea. However, this learning scheme neglects the increasing distillation difficulty of successive intermediate layers, from shallower to deeper network parts.

In this paper we introduce InDistill, a method that addresses the aforementioned limitations (details in Fig. 1). We argue that a properly designed pruning of the teacher’s intermediate layers, enabling direct knowledge transfer, can yield effective distillation of the teacher’s information flow paths to the student. Second, inspired by the curriculum learning field [18], we propose a simple, yet effective way to distill multiple layers from a teacher to a student model, while taking into consideration the critical learning periods [5]. Specifically, we propose that distilling each intermediate layer separately and in ascending transferring difficulty order (i.e., from shallow to deep layers) can enhance the KD effectiveness and consequently the student’s performance. The proposed method has been evaluated on a wide range of classification and retrieval tasks with the use of widely-adopted benchmarks (i.e., CIFAR-10 [19], CUB-200 [20], FashionMNIST [21], CIFAR-100 [19], and ImageNet [22]) and is found to surpass the state-of-the-art in all conducted experiments. In addition, combining InDistill with single-layer KD methods is found to enhance their performance. The main contributions of this paper are:

- A method that applies channel pruning on the teacher’s intermediate layers before distillation, enabling for the first time direct feature map transfer and consequently information flow path preservation, termed InDistill.
- A curriculum learning-based training strategy taking into consideration both the increasing distillation difficulty of successive layers and the critical learning periods of a neural network.
- A wide comparative analysis involving 10 state-of-the-art competitive methods and 5 widely-adopted benchmarks, in which InDistill achieves best performance across all experiments.

2 Related work

Knowledge distillation. The increasing need of deploying machine learning models on limited resourced hardware as well as their growing complexity has given rise to network compression [23]. KD, first proposed in [4], is an effective way for model compression with the goal to reproduce the teacher’s class probability distribution using a much faster and smaller student model. Several KD methods exploiting only the model’s output probability distributions have been proposed [24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29], ignoring the need for intermediate layer supervision, which is considered of high importance for effective KD [7].

Intermediate layers knowledge distillation. The first method that leverages feature maps of the teacher in order to provide the student with extra supervision is presented in [7]. This method transfers only one intermediate layer with the aid of feature map encoding. Similarly, Probabilistic Knowledge Transfer (PKT) [30] transfers the penultimate layer’s (one layer before classification) feature maps by matching their probability distribution. However, transferring knowledge of one intermediate layer can not capture the critical connections between the layers. To alleviate this shortcoming, the Attention Transfer (AT) [6] proposes an attention mechanism that transfers all intermediate layer representations. Similarly, the Hierarchical Self-supervised Augmented Knowledge Distillation (HSAKD) [31] employs classifiers on top of all intermediate layers to supervise the KD procedure. Furthermore, [32] introduces Contrastive Representation Distillation (CRD) which uses a contrastive loss to distill the feature maps that derive from the last convolutional layer. All previous methods consider feature map encoding in order to match teacher and student width, which collapses the architectural alignment. Thus, [33] introduces a method to effectively encode the extracted features before KD, but still the encoding is necessary. The aforementioned methods share the same shortcomings, they disregard preservation of information flow paths during distillation, they ignore the capacity gap between the models (i.e., difference in the number of learnable parameters), and they face the challenge of transferring multiple layers simultaneously.

Information flow preservation. An effort to capture the flow of information was made in [34] by generating a Flow of Solution Procedure (FSP) matrix that captures the relation between two successive layers. Additionally, [30] and [5] consider a loss function based on mutual information divergence in order to transfer the information flow paths. Also, [5] suggests a critical-periods-aware weight decay (WD) scheme that reduces the learning rate of the intermediate layers KD after each epoch, motivated by the fact that the first training epochs are responsible for the creation of the information flow paths [17].

Auxiliary teacher. Mirzadeh et al. [35] suggest the usage of an auxiliary model in order to reduce the capacity gap between teacher and student models. It should be stressed though, that they do not utilize the intermediate layers during the KD. Based on the same idea, [5] makes use of an auxiliary model to alleviate the structural differences between teacher and student.

Curriculum learning. Several fields have utilized curriculum learning approaches [36, 37, 38, 39, 40], which suggest splitting a hard task into sub-tasks and learning them sequentially based on difficulty order [41, 42]. In [43], a teacher-student curriculum learning framework for reinforcement learning is introduced, where the teacher determines the sub-tasks that the student should be trained on at each training step, while [44] proposes learning tasks sequentially for enhancing multi-task learning effectiveness. However, non of the existing curriculum learning approaches considers the model’s layers as sub-tasks of increasing difficulty or is designed with the aim to retain the informational flow paths.

Knowledge distillation & pruning. Finally, there have been a few attempts [15, 16] to combine KD and pruning [10] for model compression. However, neither the mixing techniques nor the approaches’ objectives coincide with ours. More specifically, [15] prunes some layers of a model and distills the rest, while [16] applies KD on a pruned model. Instead, we prune the teacher model in order to have equal width with the student and straightforwardly transfer intermediate layers. Additionally, none of these works intends to preserve the information flow paths by the combination of KD and pruning, as this paper does.

3 Methodology

In this section we provide the details of our method which is illustrated in Fig. 1.

3.1 Problem formulation

The problem of transferring knowledge from a teacher to a student model is formulated as follows. Let $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times h \times w}$ denote an input image with h and w height and width, respectively, $d(\cdot)$ the teacher model, and $l=1, \dots, L_d$ the layer's index. Then, $\mathbf{T}^{(l)} = d(\mathbf{X}, l) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{d,l} \times h_{d,l} \times w_{d,l}}$ denotes the teacher's l layer output, where $n_{d,l}$, $h_{d,l}$, and $w_{d,l}$ is its number of channels and spatial dimensions. Accordingly, consider a student model $g(\cdot)$ with θ learnable parameters, L_g layers and $\mathbf{S}^{(l)} = g(\mathbf{X}, l) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{g,l} \times h_{g,l} \times w_{g,l}}$ the l layer's output. In addition, let $\mathbf{q}_t, \mathbf{q}_s \in \mathbb{R}^C$ be the class probability distributions of the teacher and student model, respectively, with C the number of output classes. Then, the goal of single-layer KD is either to match teacher's and student's class probability distributions ($\mathbf{q}_t \simeq \mathbf{q}_s$) or to force penultimate layer representations to share maximum amount of information, namely $\max_{\theta} \mathcal{I}(\mathbf{T}^{(L_d)}; \mathbf{S}^{(L_g)})$. In addition to that, the intermediate layer KD provides an extra supervision to the main target by matching several teacher's and student's intermediate layer pairs.

In cases of teacher-student pairs with large capacity gap, different number of layers $L_d \neq L_g$ or structurally different architectures (e.g., a teacher with and a student without residual connections), we follow other works [35, 5] that make use of an auxiliary model built from the teacher model using typical knowledge distillation. $f(\cdot)$ denotes the auxiliary model, L_f the number of layers (here $L_f=L_g$), and $\mathbf{A}^{(l)} = f(\mathbf{X}, l) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{f,l} \times h_{f,l} \times w_{f,l}}$ its output feature maps. Note that $h_{f,l}=h_{g,l}$ and $w_{f,l}=w_{g,l}$ as the networks share kernel sizes. Finally, auxiliary's class probability distributions are denoted by \mathbf{q}_a .

3.2 Channel pruning

Channel pruning is used here to improve the effectiveness of KD, by forcing architectural alignment. The typical criterion for evaluating the importance of a filter is the l_1 -norm or l_2 -norm [45, 46, 10]. Here, we opt for the approach proposed in [10] that applies structured channel pruning based on l_1 -norm. Specifically, let $\mathbf{F}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times h_i \times w_i}$ denote the input features and $\mathbf{F}_o \in \mathbb{R}^{n_o \times h_o \times w_o}$ denote the output features of a layer, respectively. The layer's kernel can be denoted by $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times n_o \times k \times k}$, where k is the kernel size. Then, we follow the pruning procedure described in Alg. 1.

Algorithm 1 Channel pruning procedure

- 1: **Inputs:** filters \mathbf{K} and the number of filters to prune p . **Output:** the pruned filters $\mathbf{K}' \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times (n_o-p) \times k \times k}$.
 - 2: **procedure** PRUNE(\mathbf{K}, p)
 - 3: **for** $i \in \mathbf{K}$ **do**
 - 4: $s_i \leftarrow \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \sum_{l=1}^k \sum_{m=1}^k |\mathbf{K}_{j,i,l,m}|$
 - 5: **end for**
 - 6: $\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x} \leftarrow \text{sort}(\mathbf{s})$ $\triangleright \mathbf{x}$ denotes the sorted indices array
 - 7: $\mathbf{x} \leftarrow \mathbf{x} \setminus \mathbf{x}[1:p]$ \triangleright remove the first p indices
 - 8: $\mathbf{K}' \leftarrow \mathbf{K}[\mathbf{x}]$
 - 9: **return** \mathbf{K}'
 - 10: **end procedure**
-

3.3 Information flow-preserving KD

In cases that an auxiliary teacher is necessary (see Sec. 3.1), we design it to have the same number of layers and the same number of output channels as the student, after applying pruning with pruning rate q to all intermediate layers. As a result, the auxiliary model's feature maps sizes $n_{f,l}$ depend on the student model's feature maps sizes $n_{g,l}$ and the pruning rate $q \in [0, 1)$, namely $n_{f,l} = \frac{n_{g,l}}{1-q}$. Having designed the auxiliary model, typical KD [4] is applied to transfer the knowledge from the teacher model to the auxiliary model. The following parts of the methodology are identically applied to cases with and without an auxiliary teacher, thus we keep the teacher's notation for simplicity.

Channel pruning (see Sec. 3.2) is applied to all teacher's intermediate layers to force architectural alignment. After applying Alg. 1 with $p = q \cdot n_{d,l}$, the teacher's pruned feature maps $\mathbf{P}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{g,l} \times h_{g,l} \times w_{g,l}}$ are of equal size to the student's feature maps, which allows for direct knowledge transfer involving no encoding. The loss between models'

feature maps, $\mathbf{P}^{(l)}$ and $\mathbf{S}^{(l)}$ is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{MSE}^{(l)} = \|\mathbf{P}^{(l)} - \mathbf{S}^{(l)}\|_2^2, \quad (1)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the l_2 -norm. Given that InDistill is only applied to intermediate layers, any of the existing KD methods can be employed for the last layer. Considering the original KD method [4] that transfers the class probability distributions using the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence loss, let \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{v} denote the teacher’s and student’s logits, respectively. Then, the teacher’s and student’s probability distributions are defined by Eq. 2 and Eq. 3, respectively:

$$\mathbf{q}_{t,i} = \frac{e^{\mathbf{u}_i/T}}{\sum_j e^{\mathbf{u}_j/T}} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{q}_{s,i} = \frac{e^{\mathbf{v}_i/T}}{\sum_j e^{\mathbf{v}_j/T}}, \quad (3)$$

where T is the temperature term. Finally, the KL loss is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{KL} = \sum_i \mathbf{q}_{t,i} (\log \mathbf{q}_{t,i} - \log \mathbf{q}_{s,i}) \cdot T^2, \quad (4)$$

3.4 Curriculum learning

Curriculum learning suggests to divide a hard task into sub-tasks w.r.t. their difficulty and perform training sequentially in ascending difficulty order. When applying intermediate layers KD, one could hypothesize that transferring shallow layers is easier than transferring deep layers, for two reasons. First, shallow layers hold in general low-level information (e.g., edges and corners) while deep layers hold task-specific high-level information. Second, deep layers’ transfer requires also transferring the knowledge obtained by all previous layers as well as the information flow paths until then. Figure 2 exemplifies the higher loss when transferring deeper layers, empirically validating this intuition.

Given the above, we propose a curriculum learning scheme that considers the transferring of each layer as a separate sub-task. Particularly, let L_g be the number of layers (i.e., sub-tasks), that determine the training schedule. If the total number of training epochs is E , then the number of epochs that corresponds to each sub-task (i.e., layer) can be calculated as follows:

$$e_i = \begin{cases} a + ib & i \neq L_g \\ E - \sum_{i=1}^{L_g-1} e_i & i = L_g \end{cases}, i \in \{1, 2, \dots, L_g\}, \quad (5)$$

where parameter a indicates a threshold for each layer’s training epochs and b is a parameter that increments number of epochs w.r.t. the sub-task’s difficulty. Also, the set of epochs that corresponds to each sub-task i is $\mathcal{S}_i = \{r_i + 1, r_i + 2, \dots, r_i + e_i\}$ where:

$$r_i = \begin{cases} 0 & i = 1 \\ \sum_{k=1}^{i-1} e_k & i > 1 \end{cases}, i \in \{1, 2, \dots, L_g\}. \quad (6)$$

Figure 2: \mathcal{L}_{MSE} loss curves (see Eq. 1) on CIFAR-10 (see Sec. 4.1) validation set, while transferring 1st, 2nd, and 3rd layers.

By adopting the proposed curriculum learning scheme, the first $\sum_{i=1}^{L_g-1} e_i$ epochs are dedicated to the intermediate layers KD. In particular, the final loss is calculated as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \begin{cases} \mathcal{L}_{MSE}^{(i)} & i \neq L_g, i \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, L_g\}, \\ \mathcal{L}_{task} & i = L_g \end{cases}, \quad (7)$$

where \mathcal{L}_{task} denotes the distillation loss. This way, the student model can effectively form the critical connections that significantly facilitate the KD task.

4 Experimental setup

4.1 Datasets

The proposed method has been evaluated on five benchmark datasets: a) CIFAR-10 [19], an image dataset with 60,000 images of 10 classes that depict animals and means of transport; b) CUB-200 [20], which contains 11,788 images of 200 subcategories belonging to bird species; c) FashionMNIST [21], which consists of 70,000 grayscale images with size 28×28 that depict 10 fashion categories; d) CIFAR-100 [19], which has the same size as CIFAR-10 but comprises 100 classes (i.e., 600 samples per class); e) ImageNet [22], which includes 1.28 million training and 50,000 validation images in 1000 classes.

4.2 Competitive methods

We compare InDistill with 10 state-of-the-art KD approaches. The single-layer KD baselines that we consider for comparison are the original KD method (OKD) [4], the knowledge distillation via Softmax Regression Representation Learning (SRRL) [47] that utilizes knowledge distillation for metric learning, the Teacher Assistant Knowledge Distillation (TAKD) [35] involving an auxiliary model to enhance KD effectiveness, the Metric Knowledge Transfer (MKT) [48], the Probabilistic Knowledge Transfer (PKT) [30], and the Contrastive Representation Distillation (CRD) [32]). As intermediate KD methods we consider the Hints based approach [7], the Attention Transfer (AT) [6], and the Heterogeneous PKT with CRITICAL learning periods awareness (PKT-H-CR) [5]. Additionally, in our analysis we consider competitive methods that claim to preserve the teacher’s information flow such as the Flow of Solution Procedure (FSP) [34], the PKT, and the PKT-H-CR methods. More details regarding the aforementioned methods can be found in Sec. 2. Finally, it is worth noting that we had to conduct all experiments in Sec. 5, as none of the competitive methods uses the same teacher/student architectures to present the reported results.

4.3 Model architectures

We consider model architectures of limited capacity for CIFAR-10, CUB-200, and FashionMNIST, being small-scale and less complex. The ResNet-18 is used as the teacher model (consisting of around 11 million trainable parameters) and a tiny CNN consisting of 3 convolutional layers is used as the student model (CNN-S). Due to the structural differences as well as the large capacity gap between teacher and student we additionally consider an auxiliary teacher model (CNN-A), as described in Sec. 3.3. Table 1 presents the model architectures in detail. The images of CUB-200 have much larger size than CIFAR-10 and FashionMNIST, thus the CNN-A and CNN-S kernel sizes are adjusted accordingly. For CNN-A and CNN-S, batch normalization is applied after each convolutional layer.

Due to the capacity limitations of tiny CNNs we consider larger architectures for CIFAR-100 and ImageNet, being more complex and large-scale. ResNet32 \times 4 and ResNet32 were selected as teacher and student for CIFAR-100, while ResNet-50 and ResNet-18 were selected as teacher and student for ImageNet. Using an auxiliary teacher is redundant

model	conv (#filters, #kernel)			fc (#neurons)	
CIFAR-10 and FashionMNIST					
CNN-A	16, 3 \times 3	32, 3 \times 3	64, 3 \times 3	128	#classes
CNN-S	8, 3 \times 3	16, 3 \times 3	32, 3 \times 3	64	#classes
CUB-200					
CNN-A	16, 9 \times 9	32, 5 \times 5	64, 5 \times 5	128	#classes
CNN-S	8, 9 \times 9	16, 5 \times 5	32, 5 \times 5	64	#classes

Table 1: Auxiliary and student model architectures for CIFAR-10, FashionMNIST, and CUB-200. Convolutional and fully connected layers are abbreviated as "conv" and "fc", respectively.

for these datasets, as the teacher and student models belong to the same model family (ResNets) and the capacity gap between them is not significant. Furthermore, note that channel pruning is applied at the last layer of each block instead of each layer, thus enabling to apply InDistill to ResNets of different depth.

4.4 Implementation details and evaluation protocol

The same training protocol was used for CIFAR-10, CUB-200, and FashionMNIST datasets. In particular, the models are trained using the Adam optimizer for 60 epochs with learning rate 0.001 and for 10 epochs with learning rate 0.0001. The batch size is set to 128 and the parameters a and b are set to 2 and 1, respectively. For CIFAR-100, the models are trained for 240 epochs using the SGD optimizer with 0.9 momentum and 0.05 learning rate for the first 150 epochs, then the learning rate decays every 30 epochs by a factor of 10. The batch size is equal to 64 and the weight decay is 0.0005. For ImageNet, the models are trained for 100 epochs using the SGD optimizer with 0.9 momentum and 0.1 learning rate, while the learning rate decays every 30 epochs by a factor of 10. The batch size is equal to 64, and the weight decay is 0.0001. Also, note that gradient accumulation [49] is adopted, updating the gradients every 4 steps (i.e., 256 samples). It should be stressed that we did not perform any hyperparameter tuning on ImageNet and CIFAR-100 due to limited resources. The parameters a and b , are set to 5 and 1, respectively.

For the retrieval experiments we utilize the distillation loss considered by each method, while for the classification experiments we additionally utilize the cross-entropy loss. Unless stated otherwise, for the InDistill method, the PKT is selected as distillation loss. All the experiments were conducted using one NVIDIA RTX-3060 GPU.

The official train/test splits were used for evaluation. For the CUB-200 dataset, only the first 30 classes were used in the conducted experiments, as in [5]. For the metric learning evaluation, the mAP and the Precision@k metrics are reported, while accuracy is reported for the classification task. Finally, we also evaluate the methods w.r.t. information flow preservation. The information flow of a network can be modeled through Mutual Information (MI) [5]. MI divergence loss proposed in PKT[30] aims at minimizing the MI divergence between teacher and student, thus forcing the student model to mimic the teacher’s information flow paths. Hence, we consider it here as a measure of information flow preservation and denote it as \mathcal{L}_{MI} .

5 Results

5.1 Evaluation on standard benchmarks

Table 2 compares the performance of InDistill with that of 10 competing KD methods. The baseline performance of teacher, auxiliary, and student models is presented in the *baseline* rows, while comparison among the methods is illustrated in the *competitive* rows, for all datasets. The baseline performance of teacher and student models refers to from-scratch training without involving KD, while for the auxiliary baseline refers to its performance after applying KD from the teacher model. The proposed method consistently outperforms the competitive methods on all datasets. Specifically, for the mAP metric¹, InDistill achieves relative improvement of 3.08%, 14.27%, and 1% in comparison to state-of-the-art for CIFAR-10, CUB-200, and FashionMNIST, respectively. Also, it outperforms the baseline student by far in most cases, while many competitive methods produce close and even worse results. Surprisingly, InDistill outperforms even the auxiliary teacher on CUB-200.

Apart from the metric learning evaluation, InDistill is further evaluated at a classification setting considering three well-known benchmarks and the same competitive methods. As it can be seen in Tab. 3, InDistill outperforms the competition on all datasets, achieving 74.13%, 45.69%, and 90.57% accuracy for CIFAR-10, CUB-200, and FashionMNIST, respectively. Finally, in terms of latency the students’ mean inference time is $14.89\times$ faster than teacher (i.e., 0.49ms on CPU) and in terms of storage requirements their mean size is 28KB while the teachers’ size is 42.7MB.

Note that for CIFAR-10, we used the pretrained baselines being provided by [5], which does not hold for CUB-200 and FashionMNIST. Also, we do not report results for the CRD method on CUB-200, as we could not recreate their custom data loading procedure for this specific case.

5.2 Evaluation on challenging benchmarks

Furthermore, we conducted experiments on ImageNet and CIFAR-100 in order to evaluate InDistill on more challenging benchmarks. More precisely, we conducted the experiments on ImageNet to showcase the effectiveness of our approach

¹The presented values are calculated based on cosine similarity. Euclidean distance exhibits almost identical ranking results with InDistill outperforming the rest of methods and with only a few ranking differences among them. We opt for presenting the former as it consistently provides higher scores for all methods.

			mAP	P@k	#parameters
CIFAR-10	baseline	Teacher	90.47	92.26	11,181,642
		Auxiliary	66.78	75.91	57,994
		Student	39.00	58.77	15,050
	competitive	OKD [4]	39.38	58.54	15,050
		Hints [7]	37.64	55.06	
		AT [6]	39.67	58.74	
		MKT [48]	46.88	61.14	
		FSP [34]	37.66	57.41	
		TAKD [35]	49.29	61.37	
		SRRL [47]	52.71	63.54	
		PKT [30]	51.41	62.56	
CRD [32]		47.11	61.64		
PKT-H-CR [5]		53.00	64.06		
InDistill	54.61	65.40			
CUB-200	baseline	Teacher	66.53	71.09	11,191,902
		Auxiliary	27.27	36.64	104,990
		Student	21.21	29.97	28,318
	competitive	OKD [4]	23.84	33.17	28,318
		Hints [7]	19.18	27.15	
		AT [6]	24.11	33.18	
		MKT [48]	22.42	30.89	
		FSP [34]	21.87	30.02	
		TAKD [35]	23.98	32.92	
		SRRL [47]	20.98	28.78	
		PKT [30]	23.49	32.87	
PKT-H-CR [5]		25.15	34.46		
InDistill		28.74	38.56		
FashionMNIST	baseline	Teacher	79.49	90.94	11,175,370
		Auxiliary	74.39	86.15	57,706
		Student	68.28	86.22	14,906
	competitive	OKD [4]	68.90	85.13	14,906
		Hints [7]	69.44	85.32	
		MKT [48]	71.10	85.88	
		AT [6]	69.32	85.04	
		FSP [34]	66.41	85.00	
		TAKD [35]	69.08	85.38	
		SRRL [47]	69.53	81.23	
		PKT [30]	71.50	83.34	
CRD [32]		71.65	85.26		
PKT-H-CR [5]		71.96	84.19		
InDistill	72.68	86.08			

Table 2: Metric learning evaluation of InDistill and 10 competitive KD methods on CIFAR-10, CUB-200, and FashionMNIST. We denote Precision@k with "P@k", where k=100 for CIFAR-10 and FashionMNIST, and k=10 for CUB-200.

on a large-scale setting and on CIFAR-100 to evaluate it on a higher-complexity setting, utilizing deeper teacher and student models. Table 4 presents the performance of InDistill in comparison to 4 competitive KD approaches, on both datasets. We opt for PKT-H-CR for comparison as it exhibits the second best performance in the majority of standard benchmark experiments, and the other three (OKD, PKT, CRD) to showcase the positive effect of InDistill when combined with single layer KD methods (all highly-cited and in general well-performing). For ImageNet, InDistill with the original KD loss outperforms all competitive methods, while for CIFAR-100 it exhibits the best performance among competition when utilizing the distillation loss from CRD, except for the mAP metric for which InDistill (OKD) provides the best performance. Also, we observe that the proposed approach is successfully combined with other KD methods, enhancing their performance in both metric learning and classification settings. It is worth noting that given

method	accuracy		
	CIFAR-10	CUB-200	FashionMNIST
OKD [4]	73.08	39.32	90.01
Hints [7]	72.54	30.08	89.19
AT [6]	73.22	39.45	90.19
MKT [48]	69.32	33.33	88.03
FSP [34]	71.14	37.58	89.37
TAKD [35]	73.53	38.20	89.49
SRRL [47]	71.42	36.07	88.15
PKT [30]	73.27	40.32	90.19
PKT-H-CR [5]	73.33	42.32	90.26
CRD [32]	71.99	-	89.14
InDistill	74.13	45.69	90.57

Table 3: Classification accuracy for InDistill and 10 competitive approaches on CIFAR-10, CUB-200, and FashionM-NIST.

method	mAP	P@100	accuracy
ImageNet			
OKD [4]	30.91	31.98	71.33
InDistill (OKD)	31.52	32.53	71.54
PKT-H-CR [5]	21.92	23.86	68.86
PKT [30]	24.67	26.41	70.66
InDistill (PKT)	25.75	27.46	70.98
CRD [32]	25.99	27.46	70.49
InDistill (CRD)	31.10	32.19	71.36
CIFAR-100			
OKD [4]	56.59	65.08	72.11
InDistill (OKD)	59.79	67.45	72.96
PKT-H-CR [5]	46.40	58.52	70.36
PKT [30]	53.20	64.01	72.68
InDistill (PKT)	54.54	64.78	72.77
CRD [32]	51.34	63.19	73.70
InDistill (CRD)	58.40	67.98	73.97

Table 4: Metric learning and classification evaluation on ImageNet and CIFAR-100. ResNet-50 as teacher and ResNet-18 as student are selected for the ImageNet dataset, while ResNet32 \times 4 as teacher and ResNet32 as student are selected for the CIFAR-100 dataset. For InDistill, the parenthesis mentions the method name that the distillation loss \mathcal{L}_{task} derives from.

our limited resources, we were not able to perform hyperparameter tuning on this set of experiments which could result in even better performance for InDistill.

5.3 Preserving information flow

In Fig. 3, we present the \mathcal{L}_{MI} loss curves to assess the proposed method’s capability to distill the teacher’s information flow. In particular, the loss curves of InDistill without learning scheme (i.e., transferring all layers simultaneously), with the WD scheme [5], and with the curriculum learning scheme, are depicted for comparison. Although InDistill without learning scheme reduces \mathcal{L}_{MI} during the first training epochs (when the critical connections are created) compared to the baseline PKT method, it impedes the learning process during the last training epochs and achieves 51.54% mAP. On the contrary, applying a learning scheme aware of the critical learning periods, such as WD and the proposed learning scheme, can successfully address this limitation. However, the proposed scheme is superior to WD, as not only is aware of the critical learning periods but it also takes into account the complexity of transferring multiple layers. This can also be confirmed by the mAP values being 54.61% and 53.91% for the proposed scheme and WD, respectively. Thus, we confirm that forcing the architectural alignment and being aware of the layers’ successive transferring difficulty enables the student model to mimic the teacher’s information flow effectively. Furthermore, Tab. 5 presents the \mathcal{L}_{MI} of InDistill in comparison to other methods which also aim at preserving the teacher’s flow. InDistill presents the lowest MI divergence on all datasets, which confirms that InDistill enables the student model to simulate the teacher’s information flow better.

Figure 3: The \mathcal{L}_{MI} loss curves during KD on CIFAR-10.

method	CIFAR-10	CUB-200	FashionMNIST
FSP [34]	0.2760	0.0566	0.4419
PKT [30]	0.1270	0.0406	0.0986
PKT-H-CR [5]	0.1063	0.0381	0.0689
InDistill	0.0972	0.0236	0.0199

Table 5: The \mathcal{L}_{MI} loss on CIFAR-10, CUB-200 and FashionMNIST test sets.

5.4 Ablation study

In Tab. 6, we illustrate the impact of \mathcal{L}_{task} selection on InDistill’s performance and information flow preservation level. In this analysis, \mathcal{L}_{task} can be the distillation loss function considered in OKD, CRD and PKT methods. As it is observed, information flow preservation and performance both score best when considering the PKT’s distillation loss. Also, a big difference from the second method, being CRD for both, is observed. Note that this result does not hold for ImageNet or CIFAR-100 though, in which InDistill outperforms the competition but the optimal setting in terms of \mathcal{L}_{task} is different for each case (see Tab. 4). Identifying potential dataset-specific criteria that lead to an optimal choice without the burden of ablation is considered by the authors as future work.

Table 7 presents how InDistill’s components (i.e., teacher pruning and curriculum learning) cumulatively affect the student’s performance. The first row (B) refers to typical final layer distillation using an unpruned auxiliary teacher, the second row (B+P) refers to pruning the auxiliary teacher but distilling all layers simultaneously, the third row (B+C) refers to distilling the unpruned auxiliary teacher’s layers using curriculum learning and the forth row (B+P+C) refers to pruning the auxiliary teacher and then applying curriculum learning (i.e., InDistill). As already demonstrated in Fig. 3, pruning contributes to the critical connections’ creation during the first training epochs, but eventually hinders the training procedure, which is also reflected in the results of Tab. 7. On the contrary, pruning combined with curriculum learning enables the critical connections formation as well as the effective learning of the final task, and results in considerably enhanced student’s performance.

In Tab. 8, we present how the pruning rate selection, affects InDistill’s performance in terms of mAP. Pruning half of the channels per layer provides an optimal trade-off, while the other two rates (i.e., 1/3 and 0.75) exhibit competitive

method	\mathcal{L}_{MI}	mAP
InDistill (OKD)	0.2242	42.38
InDistill (CRD)	0.1856	48.24
InDistill (PKT)	0.0972	54.61

Table 6: The \mathcal{L}_{MI} loss and the mAP score computed on CIFAR-10, for InDistill utilizing OKD, PKT, and CRD loss functions.

method	CIFAR-10	CUB-200	FashionMNIST
B	51.41	23.49	71.50
B+P	51.54	24.76	71.57
B+C	53.49	25.96	72.02
B+P+C	54.61	28.74	72.68

Table 7: The mAP score on CIFAR-10, CUB-200, and FashionMNIST test sets, for InDistill’s components ablation. “B” denotes baseline, “P” denotes pruning the auxiliary teacher and “C” denotes curriculum learning training scheme.

q	CIFAR-10	CUB-200	FashionMNIST
1/3	53.60	27.62	72.64
1/2	54.61	28.74	72.68
3/4	54.34	28.33	72.48

Table 8: InDistill’s performance (mAP) vs. pruning rate q on CIFAR-10, CUB-200 and FashionMNIST test sets.

performance. Note that we opt for these pruning rates because they result in an integer number of channels. In addition, investigating extreme pruning rates (close to 1) is meaningless due to their severe impact on the auxiliary model’s width. Also, $q=0$ means no pruning is applied. Further hyperparameter tuning analysis can be found in the supplementary material.

6 Conclusions

In this work, we propose a model compression methodology combining knowledge distillation and channel pruning with the aim of effectively transferring the teacher’s information flow paths to the student. In particular, we apply channel pruning to the teacher in order to match the student’s size and proceed with direct transfer of intermediate layers. In this way, architectural alignment is forced enabling the teacher’s information flow paths to be effectively transferred to the student. In addition, we adopt a curriculum learning-based training approach to achieve awareness of the increasing transferring difficulty of successive layers as well as the critical learning periods during which the information flow paths are created. The above strategy performs best among many state-of-the-art methods on a wide range of retrieval as well as classification experiments. Also, it is empirically validated that our method retains the information flow paths more effectively than competition.

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References

- [1] Tejalal Choudhary, Vipul Mishra, Anurag Goswami, and Jagannathan Sarangapani. A comprehensive survey on model compression and acceleration. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 53(7):5113–5155, 2020.
- [2] Yu Cheng, Duo Wang, Pan Zhou, and Tao Zhang. Model compression and acceleration for deep neural networks: The principles, progress, and challenges. *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, 35(1):126–136, 2018.
- [3] Jianping Gou, Baosheng Yu, Stephen J Maybank, and Dacheng Tao. Knowledge distillation: A survey. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 129(6):1789–1819, 2021.
- [4] Geoffrey Hinton, Oriol Vinyals, and Jeff Dean. Distilling the knowledge in a neural network. *stat*, 1050:9, 2015.
- [5] Nikolaos Passalis, Maria Tzelepi, and Anastasios Tefas. Heterogeneous knowledge distillation using information flow modeling. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 2339–2348, 2020.
- [6] Sergey Zagoruyko and Nikos Komodakis. Paying more attention to attention: Improving the performance of convolutional neural networks via attention transfer. In *5th International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2017.
- [7] Adriana Romero, Nicolas Ballas, Samira Ebrahimi Kahou, Antoine Chassang, Carlo Gatta, and Yoshua Bengio. Fitnets: Hints for thin deep nets. In *3rd International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2015.
- [8] Tailin Liang, John Glossner, Lei Wang, Shaobo Shi, and Xiaotong Zhang. Pruning and quantization for deep neural network acceleration: A survey. *Neurocomputing*, 461:370–403, 2021.

- [9] Xiaolong Ma, Geng Yuan, Sheng Lin, Zhengang Li, Hao Sun, and Yanzhi Wang. Resnet can be pruned 60×: Introducing network purification and unused path removal (p-rm) after weight pruning. In *IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Nanoscale Architectures*, pages 1–2. IEEE, 2019.
- [10] Hao Li, Asim Kadav, Igor Durdanovic, Hanan Samet, and Hans Peter Graf. Pruning filters for efficient convnets. In *5th International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2017.
- [11] Jian-Hao Luo, Jianxin Wu, and Weiyao Lin. Thinet: A filter level pruning method for deep neural network compression. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 5058–5066, 2017.
- [12] Xiaohan Ding, Tianxiang Hao, Jianchao Tan, Ji Liu, Jungong Han, Yuchen Guo, and Guiguang Ding. Resrep: Lossless cnn pruning via decoupling remembering and forgetting. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 4510–4520, 2021.
- [13] Zhiqiang Chen, Ting-Bing Xu, Changde Du, Cheng-Lin Liu, and Huiguang He. Dynamical channel pruning by conditional accuracy change for deep neural networks. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 32(2):799–813, 2020.
- [14] Zi Wang, Chengcheng Li, and Xiangyang Wang. Convolutional neural network pruning with structural redundancy reduction. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 14913–14922, 2021.
- [15] Nima Aghli and Eraldo Ribeiro. Combining weight pruning and knowledge distillation for cnn compression. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 3191–3198, 2021.
- [16] Shi Chen and Qi Zhao. Shallowing deep networks: Layer-wise pruning based on feature representations. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 41(12):3048–3056, 2018.
- [17] Alessandro Achille, Matteo Rovere, and Stefano Soatto. Critical learning periods in deep networks. In *7th International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2019.
- [18] Yoshua Bengio. *Learning deep architectures for AI*. Now Publishers Inc, 2009.
- [19] Alex Krizhevsky. Learning multiple layers of features from tiny images. *Technical Report*, 2009.
- [20] Catherine Wah, Steve Branson, Peter Welinder, Pietro Perona, and Serge Belongie. *The caltech-ucsd birds-200-2011 dataset*. CNS-TR-2010-001, California Institute of Technology, 2011.
- [21] Han Xiao, Kashif Rasul, and Roland Vollgraf. Fashion-mnist: a novel image dataset for benchmarking machine learning algorithms. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1708.07747*, 2017.
- [22] Jia Deng, Wei Dong, Richard Socher, Li-Jia Li, Kai Li, and Li Fei-Fei. Imagenet: A large-scale hierarchical image database. In *2009 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 248–255. IEEE, 2009.
- [23] Cristian Bucilua, Rich Caruana, and Alexandru Niculescu-Mizil. Model compression. In *Proceedings of the 12th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, pages 535–541, 2006.
- [24] Seung Wook Kim and Hyo-Eun Kim. Transferring knowledge to smaller network with class-distance loss. In *5th International Conference on Learning Representations Workshop*, 2017.
- [25] Rafael Müller, Simon Kornblith, and Geoffrey E Hinton. When does label smoothing help? *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 32, 2019.
- [26] Zhong Meng, Jinyu Li, Yong Zhao, and Yifan Gong. Conditional teacher-student learning. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing*, pages 6445–6449. IEEE, 2019.
- [27] Xiatian Zhu, Shaogang Gong, et al. Knowledge distillation by on-the-fly native ensemble. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 31, 2018.
- [28] Dae Young Park, Moon-Hyun Cha, Daesin Kim, Bohyung Han, et al. Learning student-friendly teacher networks for knowledge distillation. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 34, 2021.
- [29] Xiang Deng and Zhongfei Zhang. Comprehensive knowledge distillation with causal intervention. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 34, 2021.
- [30] Nikolaos Passalis and Anastasios Tefas. Learning deep representations with probabilistic knowledge transfer. In *Proceedings of the European Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 268–284, 2018.
- [31] Chuanguang Yang, Zhulin An, Linhang Cai, and Yongjun Xu. Hierarchical self-supervised augmented knowledge distillation. In *Proceedings of the 13th International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, pages 1217–1223, 2021.
- [32] Yonglong Tian, Dilip Krishnan, and Phillip Isola. Contrastive representation distillation. In *7th International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2019.
- [33] Jangho Kim, SeongUk Park, and Nojun Kwak. Paraphrasing complex network: Network compression via factor transfer. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 31, 2018.
- [34] Junho Yim, Donggyu Joo, Jihoon Bae, and Junmo Kim. A gift from knowledge distillation: Fast optimization, network minimization and transfer learning. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 4133–4141, 2017.

- [35] Seyed Iman Mirzadeh, Mehrdad Farajtabar, Ang Li, Nir Levine, Akihiro Matsukawa, and Hassan Ghasemzadeh. Improved knowledge distillation via teacher assistant. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, pages 5191–5198, 2020.
- [36] Alex Graves, Marc G Bellemare, Jacob Menick, Remi Munos, and Koray Kavukcuoglu. Automated curriculum learning for neural networks. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 1311–1320, 2017.
- [37] Petru Soviany, Radu Tudor Ionescu, Paolo Rota, and Nicu Sebe. Curriculum learning: A survey. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, pages 1–40, 2022.
- [38] Chen Gong, Dacheng Tao, Stephen J Maybank, Wei Liu, Guoliang Kang, and Jie Yang. Multi-modal curriculum learning for semi-supervised image classification. *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, 25(7):3249–3260, 2016.
- [39] Faisal Khan, Bilge Mutlu, and Jerry Zhu. How do humans teach: On curriculum learning and teaching dimension. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 24, 2011.
- [40] Jiwen Zhang, Jianqing Fan, Jiajie Peng, et al. Curriculum learning for vision-and-language navigation. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 34, 2021.
- [41] Yoshua Bengio, Jérôme Louradour, Ronan Collobert, and Jason Weston. Curriculum learning. In *Proceedings of the 26th annual International Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 41–48, 2009.
- [42] Wojciech Zaremba and Ilya Sutskever. Learning to execute. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1410.4615*, 2014.
- [43] Tabet Matiisen, Avital Oliver, Taco Cohen, and John Schulman. Teacher–student curriculum learning. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 31(9):3732–3740, 2019.
- [44] Anastasia Pentina, Viktoriia Sharmanska, and Christoph H Lampert. Curriculum learning of multiple tasks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 5492–5500, 2015.
- [45] Wei Wen, Chunpeng Wu, Yandan Wang, Yiran Chen, and Hai Li. Learning structured sparsity in deep neural networks. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 29, 2016.
- [46] Song Han, Jeff Pool, John Tran, and William Dally. Learning both weights and connections for efficient neural network. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 28, 2015.
- [47] Jing Yang, Brais Martinez, Adrian Bulat, Georgios Tzimiropoulos, et al. Knowledge distillation via softmax regression representation learning. In *9th International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2021.
- [48] Lu Yu, Vacit Oguz Yazici, Xialei Liu, Joost van de Weijer, Yongmei Cheng, and Arnau Ramisa. Learning metrics from teachers: Compact networks for image embedding. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 2907–2916, 2019.
- [49] Joeri R Hermans, Gerasimos Spanakis, and Rico Möckel. Accumulated gradient normalization. In *Asian Conference on Machine Learning*, pages 439–454. PMLR, 2017.

A Supplementary material

Figure 1: (a) Comparison between InDistill and PKT-H-CR for auxiliary/student models of different depth. (b) InDistill student performance for different values of α and b on CIFAR-10, in terms of mAP.

We evaluate InDistill using 4 different auxiliary/student model pairs, that vary in terms of depth. Except for the auxiliary and student models with 3 convolutional layers that we use at the conducted experiments reported in the main manuscript, we also design 3 additional model pairs that consist of 2, 5, and 7 layers, respectively. The number of their trainable parameters varies from 3,706 to 1,131,262 and it also depends on the dataset. Figure 1a demonstrates the performance of InDistill and PKT-H-CR (the second best performing method on standard benchmarks) in terms of mAP, at different model depths. The proposed method exhibits superior performance at all model depths, except for the 2-layer model on CIFAR-10 for which PKT-H-CR slightly outperforms InDistill. For the remaining model depths, the proposed method outperforms PKT-H-CR both on CIFAR-10 and CUB-200 datasets. Regarding FashionMNIST, although the performance of both methods is very close, InDistill performs slightly better at all model depths.

Figure 1b presents how the hyperparameters α and b affect the student’s performance, when applying InDistill. Assigning the value of 3 to the hyperparameter b exhibits reduced performance compared to other b values (i.e., 1 and 2). In addition, setting b equal to 2 seems to be an appropriate option for mid-range α values (i.e., 3-5). The best performance is achieved for the values 2 and 1 for α and b , respectively. Additionally, it is observed that InDistill surpasses the state-of-the-art, being 53.0% mAP with all value combinations. Finally, for the ImageNet experiments that we were not able to conduct hyperparameter tuning we opted for a higher offset, namely $\alpha=5$. Because of the dataset’s complexity, we consider providing some extra time to distill the shallower layers as beneficial for creating the critical connections.